

THE EVALUATION OF FUNCTIONAL PROPERTIES OF THE GAMES RELATED WITH HAZELNUT AND WALNUT IN THE HOPA REGION/DISTRICT, TURKEY

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Abstract:

Hopa is a kind of region with difficulties of economic life. The territorial property of the region has some boundaries for mechanical cultivation causing an effect on social life. People tried to concentrate on the activities that they got used to do in the past. The things produced, took place in their social life. The production of hazelnut and walnut, important source of agriculture, took place not only in economics and nutrition but also in life. These were used as a tool for play in addition to the art of decoration and oil industry.

Keywords: functional properties, games, Hopa region/district

1. Introduction

Hopa, district of Artvin, is located in the most eastern part of East Black Sea Region. This district is the lowest due to the height and there are no meadow and pasture area found. Hopa has a scattered settlement due to the territory. This property causes the agriculture in the region and prevents the usage of mechanical agriculture. Agriculture in the region depends on the various trees. Thus, endemic fruit agriculture comes out such as citrus, tea, hazelnut, kiwi and walnut. Hazelnut and walnut are one of the fruits

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with a hard shell. This shell has some properties in addition to the fruit property. Shell includes some components used for the treatment of some diseases and fruits inside are rich of some minerals and vitamins. Shells can be used for artistic work and can be processed for the fuel industry due to the burning properties for a long time. In addition, these are indispensable play tools for the children in the region. Play is significant for the development of children. The game is mostly collective activities, which started with the socialization of people from the primitive period, mostly emerged with imitations, sometimes preparation for war, sometimes hunting and sometimes has ritual motifs (Tuzcuoğulları, 2016). Unfortunately, nowadays playing on streets lessened and people evolve into individuality instead of collectivity. Bad thoughts come into life instead of respect to the other people, justice and equity due to the different thoughts of people. Multi-user On-Line Game attracts the interest of children, a need for socialization and elimination (Alıncak et al., 2016). However, ancient people mentioned the role of play on moral and social development by saying that play was the manor for children. (Ayan et al., 2015) Game-based physical activity (Alıncak, 2016a; 2016b; 2017) also affects healthy life style behaviors (Öner et al., 2016) and some motoric features such as flexibility (Özer et al., 2017).

The aim of this study was to reveal the role of hazelnut and walnut for the people living in Hopa and the function on social and economic life.

2. Method

Since there is a limited number of printed sources on the topic of the study, interview techniques as well as literature review were used. Interviews were conducted with individual and semi-structured technique. The data obtained in the interviews were divided into categories and the qualitative study was completed by descriptive analysis.

3. Findings

The hazelnut and walnut grown in the region have functional properties in many different fields. It is seen that they are evaluated in the field of nutrition and health, in the field of fine arts, in the fuel industry and as an indispensable tool of children's games.

Walnut and hazelnut are important nutrients for children in the age of development in terms of omega-3 oil, some minerals and vitamins. These minerals and vitamins are useful for the physical and mental development of children. Endemic plants that are unique to this region are a good source of nutrients for local children.

Again, these sources of nutrients also have an important place in the health field due to some substances they contain. They are organic foods that can benefit for heart and vascular diseases, outside of medicine. They have an important role in balancing cholesterol and preventing narrowing of vein walls. They can be useful for some types of cancer, such as colon, prostate and breast cancer. They contain very strong antioxidant elements which may be found in very few food species.

Especially, the green outer shell of walnuts has a number of functions in herbal paints and fine arts. The fruit's crust thus has the opportunity to be evaluated without throwing it away. It can be used as decoration in handicraft products.

Walnut and hazelnut shells are also used in the fuel industry. The fact that the calorific values are higher than the coal indicates an important advantage. Also, it is economically beneficial to maintain this high temperature for longer time than the coal. What hazelnut and walnut shells are collected and used in the fuel industry have become very popular in the Black Sea region (Bayraktaroğlu, 2017).

The most commonly used materials in this region are hazelnut and walnut, so they are normally included in children's plays. Games such as "ÜçTaş", "BeşTaş", "Cıncıklı Gülle", "Gülle" played in almost every region, are played with hazelnut and walnut in Hopa. But there are only games belonging to Hopa, such as "Kunkul" and "Ceviz Fırılacağı" as well as playing for fun purposes, continuing functional features after the game is over. Winning children in these games will have all the hazelnuts and walnuts in the middle or in the game (Zaim, 2017). Playing Kunkul Game especially is a good opportunity to collect hazelnuts. The children who collect the hazelnuts in the game, after a while they sell them and make allowance for them (Karabulut, 2017, Bulut, 2017). It is like a kind of tradition to leave the children who are harvested hazelnuts fallen under the trees, to encourage them to collect and to encourage them the game.

Kunkul game *"is played by combining three hazelnuts and placing one more nuts on top. The children try to scatter the hazelnut group and knock out the hazelnuts in their hands from a certain distance. The game continues until all hazelnuts are gone"*. (Acar, 2017). Unfortunately, these games are forgotten now and the old ones are left in their memory.

"CevizFırılacağı" game is played with the name of "Topaç" game in some regions. However, it plays, making some changes in the structure of the walnut in Hopa. Large and round walnuts are chosen. Walnut is pierced on both sides and the rope is rolled up and rolled up from bottom to top. It is launched like a spade. Whichever walnut turns longer than the others, he becomes the winner of the game. The agreed amount of walnut gives to the winner (Kurdoğlu, 2017). As seen, apart from

playing games, the activities which the winner takes the game tools and sells them for pocket money make a difference to the functional nature of the game tools.

4. Results

Walnut and hazelnut, which can be accepted as endemic plants growing in the town of Hopa, continue to function as a game tool in games seen rarely. In addition this, children get money by collecting nuts and walnuts thanks to these games, functionality carries to a different dimension. The use of hazelnut and walnut shells as fuel contributes to cheap energy production. While walnut and hazelnut have many important effects on health and nutrition, their contribution to economical life of the outer shells is important in terms of functionality.

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